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**EFFECTS OF MIDDLE AGES TO NON-ACTIVENESS
A Study to Identify the Obstacles and Challenges Faced by Middle Age
Population to be Physically**

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ABSTRACT

Active Aging shows the World Health Organization (WHO) about addressing the challenge facing newcomers. Information on issues and promoters of active life should be given extra attention. In addition, men appear to have less involvement in cultural activities and are less likely to prevent infertility than women. Exercise has been identified as one of the three most important behaviors that treat major chronic illnesses that continue to cause a large proportion of global deaths. Although scientific evidence suggests that the health and quality of the result of active lifestyles is increasing across the course of life, the lives of older and older adults represent the most dysfunctional part of the population. Among the objectives of this review is to discuss the benefits of active health, especially for older people; highlight the major challenges and challenges faced by exercise and aging; and explore a range of scientific, policy, and practice indicators that could have a positive impact on the significant physical unemployment challenge facing an increasing number of countries worldwide. 16 older men, wrote a diary of 7 days each. Two group discussions with the men were held. Scheduled text editing was used to analyze the information. The task completion questionnaire was used for data collection. The analysis identifies three categories that describe challenges in physical activity: "Differences between women, Doing meaningful physical activity, Environmental socio-cultural issues. The motivating situations were seen as new activities to find young friends and more details on how to deal with the situation. This study investigated peace education and violent behaviour among students of the University of Calabar, in Cross River State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of all undergraduate students of the University of Calabar, Cross River State. Accidental random sampling technique was used to select 400 respondents. A structured Peace Education and Violent Behaviour Questionnaire (PEVBQ) was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was tested and the reliability estimate of .83 was obtained. Two (2) research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and Pearson Product Moment Correlation

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technique was used to test the hypotheses. The result obtained revealed that values orientation and self-discipline significantly influence violent behaviour. Based on the findings, it was recommended largely that government should make it a policy for peace education to be taught at all levels of our school system to inculcate acceptable and healthier societal values among children and youths. This will ensure the Integration of understanding of peace, human rights, social justice and global issues throughout the curriculum.

INTRODUCTION

It has been argued that the achievement of aging, in a broad sense, may reflect evolutionary adaptations that provide seed support and other contributions to society. To fulfill such a social power, however, requires older people to maintain daily levels of energy and energy that allow them to participate in the physical and social efforts that occur through them. Unfortunately, the current aging process in many developed countries is often accompanied by severe decline in physical, mental, and / or social function leading to loss of freedom and quality of life, while contributing to significant economic costs.

In the face of these broad social challenges associated with current global aging trends, such as the cost and access to health care, obesity and its association with housing, housing, and the need for community-based services that allow adults, scientists and policymakers to focus more on identifying potential positive effects on the process. Of aging and the quality of life of older adults. One of those areas is the normal body mass. In fact, existing evidence of evolution suggests that the human species evolved by regular physical activity, and until the mid-20th century it was generally successful to do so. The increasing speed at which technological advances have passed through industrial societies has led to a unique situation where, in fact, we "emerge" from our culture of adaptation to the very different, and accommodating, conditions we find ourselves in today.

The purpose of this paper is to provide a detailed description of the contributions, at all levels of impact, of an active lifestyle for healthy aging. We discuss the global magnitude of physical inactivity of older adults, as well as the major challenges and challenges currently facing physical activity and aging, particularly in relation to successful interventions. We also recommend scientific, policy, and practice references to address the challenges described. In field negotiations, we use the general definition of "physical activity" as any body movement produced by skeletal muscle leading to energy expenditure, unlike "exercise or sport", which is often described as a physical exercise only including the organized, organized, and repetitive exercises performed to develop or to maintain one or more components of fitness. In addition to the physical exercises (e.g. walking, biking, and swimming, running) that are recommended throughout the life course, older adults can benefit from resistance exercises, stretching, and moderate exercise that meet muscle weakness, flexibility, and balance the company generally aging. Notably, research has shown that even the oldest and most fragile parts of older adults can benefit from a general increase in these types of physical activity when tailored to the needs of the participant. .

In line with the literature, we define adults as being 50 years of age and older, given the opportunities to prevent physical and mental decline and sedentary habits that increase between the middle ages and beyond. In addition, addressing these issues during the middle adolescence increases the ability to prevent the onset of chronic diseases and improve the health and quality of life throughout the long-lived population of industrialized countries.

In western society, there is a growing concern for unemployment with no adverse effect on human health. Both this policy and research over the last few decades have focused on exercise, and there are recommendations for the number of minutes a person should exercise each week. Recently, the emphasis has shifted to how a sedentary lifestyle is challenging for good health. Consequently, an understanding of the physical barriers to physical activity and how to facilitate the active daily life of the majority of people, must be taken into account. Active Aging shows a message from the WHO about tackling the challenge that people are growing so quickly. The changing demographics of the population is also challenging for the elderly. From focusing on exercise in the gym, much of the emphasis is now being placed on the positive effects of daily activities of the elderly, such as gardening and walking. Traveling in particular has received a lot of attention over the last few years. However,

different aspects of the individual's physical condition will influence this task. According to Tsai et al. movement in society between different levels of life is essential to elevating physical activity. Because walking outside is recommended for seniors, there is a need to explore how barriers, motivators and environmental factors can make traveling and spending time outdoors for older people. Better information is needed to take responsibility for one's health, and this suggests a person's physical functioning. It would be beneficial for each municipality to withstand the environment in order to address all the potential physical barriers to the population. Hazel Wandter et al. looked at the built environment and pointed out that the physical environment of each person can encourage or hinder physical activity. Jefferis et al. write about the fall as a barrier to physical activity in older men. Fear of falling is associated with a work-related siege, even more so than when someone with real knowledge is planning to fall. In addition, advice on fall prevention can be seen as a threat to people's self-esteem and independence, and may be accompanied by confusion. Experiences in the field of practice and assessment from the Norwegian primary care report, point to the differences between men and women when it comes to participating in municipal programs. Elders look very active in their daily lives, even though they suffer from many health conditions. However, men seem to play a smaller role in cultural activities and decrease in fall prevention groups. Many women work with older people in primary care, and one wonders if the services provided by older adults meet the preferences of older men. There are marked gender differences and therefore the need to provide a greater understanding of the challenges men face regarding continuing their aging activities as they age. To illustrate, what factors can influence men's participation in outdoor travel, what do they see as barriers, and what prevents them from becoming physically active as they age? How can the experience of retired men provide practical advice to health care professionals and other men when they face challenges in physical activity? The purpose of this pilot study is therefore to assess and explain the challenges and motivations of physical activity faced by retired men as they age.

Methods

To collect information about the challenges of continuing to exercise with their age seen by older men, an integrated Time Geographic Diary and Focus group discussion method was selected. Time Geographic Diary provides a tool for systematic studies of daily life activities. The notion of time in space focuses on what people do, and how daily life is shaped by what a person likes and decides to do. Participants recorded the time when they started any new activity, what the activity was, where it happened and with whom, and had the freedom to comment. In this study, they wrote the Time Geographic Diary for 1 week, complete data contained information from 63 days. This method was chosen by both as a data collection and awareness method to give them an idea of their functions. A Focus Group Discussion Method was chosen to encourage participants to explore and discuss their experiences of how to continue to work hard after retirement. This approach is ideal for gaining an understanding of how participants understand and discuss topics of interest. In addition, being among others who share much in common. Experiences in an enabling / interactive environment can enable participants to present positive and negative ideas more easily. This study was approved by the Norwegian Social Science Data Services.

Data collection

Sixteen participants wrote TGD for 1 week each. The first author met with them before they started writing to provide information and encourage them to write ideas and answer questions. The author met with them after the diary was written down to put up with the church it was a normal week and talked about their experiences and any additional comments. Meeting with each participant seemed to make them aware of the importance of the study, and perhaps even encouraged them to make more comments during the week. Studies have shown that a group size between four-eight makes it possible for everyone to participate freely in FGD. Two interviews took place in a meeting room at the Info Center in the municipality. This is a neutral meeting room in the city center. Invite all middle-aged men who had written a diary; only a few of them were present. A draft intellectual guide with open questions was sent to the participants some days before the meeting. The discussion focused on "Retired men and gymnastics" with a focus on four main things: Why is physical activity important to

you? What are your thoughts on physical activity in the years ahead? What are the essentials to staying active? What prevents you from working? Participants sat around the table and were encouraged to talk about and discuss experiences and contexts related to themes. Each session lasted for one hour and included food. In order to promote dialogue among the participants, a man with experience in conducting focus group discussions, was elected President. The first author (woman) who had met men doing TGDs, was a facilitator and did not participate in discussions and sat in the back of the room. The authors contributed to the data collection. This strategy was chosen because we believe that men talk differently to how they talk to women. By finding a man in a leadership role, we think men will talk and talk more freely. A third FGD was planned, however, when the second one ended, we got a little more detail on the top of the TGD and the first FGD came out.

Data analysis

FGDs are recorded and written verbatim, consisting of 30 pages of text. In addition, a handwritten diary was included in the analysis. Overall this includes over 100 pages of text. Since the purpose of this study was to assess challenges and facilitators, a systemic approach was selected for Systemic Text Conduction. This is a great four-step process inspired by Giorgi.

Step 1

In accordance with Matthew all the text from the FGDs was read several times to get an idea of the complete details. The coding process was started by the first author and discussed further with the authors. The emerging themes in each interview were compared to the themes identified by the first author in the written notes after each interview session and between the groups. At this point the text from the diary is added to the analysis process. Each diary text was read and re-read over and over again to gain a general understanding of the man's daily life.

Step 2

Subsequently, themes were re-read to delve deeper into information and organize translation units. In accordance with the analysis process in the text of the Systemic Code four codes appeared in the analysis process; exercise, daily activities, fitness reasons, and advice for some older men.

Step 3

By asking questions such as: What do men tell us about working in the gym? What are the obstacles to the progress of fitness they encounter? Finally, three key components were identified in the research question:

- Retired men and physical exercise
- Obstacles to physical fitness
- Physical factors that influence body function.

Step 4

After the rigorous analysis process goes back and forth, we have used a theoretical model that is used to study changes in movement, to help us understand and understand emerging phases. The model was introduced by Newell and has three distinct phases that interact with each other to find the right way to communicate and control in any task.

Results

Results are organized using Newell's model, and concludes with the following categories: Individual constraints, task constraints, environmental difficulties

Individual Obstacles

Men discussed how gender and their identity as retired men had an impact on body function, and highlighted three aspects of this. First, they found that they had difficulty displaying physical weakness. Even with the slightest seizures I feel the defect I will disclose. They admitted that they

waited longer before asking for help. This is expressed as: being taught that we men have to put up with things more than women and accept our status, even though we have heard that it is important to get help early, such as seeing a doctor or doctor here. The use of auxiliary technologies may also indicate weaknesses. Each characteristic is that most men aspire to "flex their muscles". Participants talked about enjoying privately doing better than the person next to them. For example, one said that when he started to exercise, he worked excessively for the first time and as a result, had muscle problems afterwards: In my mind I'm still in my 30's, and when I see others go faster or work harder I want to get better or better. The third scenario shows how men take preventative measures in fear of falling or hurting themselves. They had heard and read in the newspapers that the injury would take you far back, and it would take longer to cure, than when they were young. The fall could be the beginning of the end, says one man. They were terrified to fall, so they chose to let it go rather than risk it falling or getting hurt.

Ra Work Problems

The men knew that physical exercise was very important in adulthood. They read in the newspapers that they should exercise regularly. Some of them say they know they have to make a conscious and meaningful effort to take care of their health. Many insist that regular exercise should be fun and helpful. Many of them say they need regular programs and good practice to get physically active.

Local Economic Problems

Almost all men enjoyed walking, and chose to use their legs to travel as often as possible; for example, going out to find friends at a coffee shop or going to a library. In addition, some of them had the usual habit of going outside for many days, thus having physical fitness and meeting people. They said if these lanes were getting old they would have difficulty keeping up because of problems in the area like bad roads, bad weather or they needed a place to stay because they no longer trust their legs.

Conclusions

To achieve the purpose of active aging, service providers and local authorities need to have a better understanding of the issues that retired men experience as they age. This study highlights important aspects of the challenges that retired men face in maintaining their fitness levels. It is clear that the preference for middle-aged men for physical activity is influenced by gender, social role, physical and social conditions and provides some clues to the adaptation of body function. The findings of this study are important for better understanding men's challenges in old age, which is an invaluable information for service delivery in changing programs in men's preferences. Steps must be taken to municipalities to deal with environmental barriers. A senior citizen needs an address to report physical obstacles. It is important to use this knowledge in the field of practice in service delivery and in the immediate vicinity of men. The findings of gender differences will be taken into account in large-scale research projects in the field. However, further research is needed. This is in line with a previous report showing that body levels decreased with age at ≥ 52 years of age. It is reported that seniors spend only 3% of their day in PA moderate. After retirement, the overall PA decreases and the PA or financing increases.

Physical Exercise & Aging - A Natural View:

The most common types of aging, which explain the association between individual ability and the environment, have been discussed for many decades and have grown to perfection and detail. The natural framework relevant to physical activity includes examples of the individual i.e. Biologic, aesthetic, demographic), social / cultural, and environmental / environmental impact levels. The framework also includes the impact of time e.k.t. health and time effects, daily, weekly, or overtime effects that can be diagnostic and interventions and improvement or course health outcomes such as menstruation, retirement, bereavement etc. at all levels of impact. Note that a natural outline can be used to organize appropriate physiological effects e.g. health status and occupation, neighborhood or community, social capital, dictionaries such as cultural beliefs related to physical activity, neighborhood mobility and intervention i.e. developed public support for regular physical activity,

economic incentives aimed at promoting active physical health.

Benefits of Physical Activity:

Early attention has been made to the accumulation, over the past 70 years, of the scientific literature that emphasized the importance of regular physical activity on health, function and quality of life throughout the course of life. While regular physical activity has been shown to have a positive impact on health and function in all age groups, on the onset of health, a regular exercise regimen can have far-reaching effects in later years and may actually slow down the aging process. The expected increase in the chronic conditions associated with aging, and the accompanying pressure on the health care system, provides a strong argument for promoting physical activity as a primary prevention strategy. In addition to the strong association between physical inactivity and underlying cause of death, chronic illnesses and health conditions strongly associated with cardiovascular disease include heart disease, stroke, type 2 diabetes, other cancers ie colon, liver, dementia, dementia, weight loss and weight loss. Additional health areas for adult fitness that have found common physical activity include improved sleep quality, lower risk of hip fractures and osteoporosis, reduced obesity, lower risk of lung and cervical cancer, weight loss following weight loss, and well-being and quality health. Regular physical activity may help alleviate some of the side effects that are usually associated with lifestyle changes such as menopause. While clear evidence is currently lacking about the general physiological consequences of aging-related disability defined by Nagi as limitations on the roles and functions of the social and physical community and at least one large randomized controlled trial, Interventional Living and Adulthood are currently underway in the United States to directly answer this question.

To insert a natural outline: body stems are related to:

Opportunities among older adults for continued employment or volunteering activities may influence the strength, quality of life and indirectly, health behavior such as physical activity. For example, a pilot study of an elementary school volunteer program in a US community called Experience Corps was designed to promote physical activity and understanding and enjoyment among older volunteers while improving academic achievement, found a marked increase in physical activity, energy, perceived social resources, and cognitive function over 4-8 months related to control.

The biggest challenges currently facing physical activity and aging are:

- ❖ Lack of a functional way of thinking about physical activity solutions
- ❖ A clear lack of evidence to promote body-based physical activity
- ❖ Addressing health disparities as part of physical activity and the aging agenda
- ❖ Autonomy behavior as a separate learning goal and intervention intervention

Recommended guidelines for increasing physical activity:

The magnitude and increasing severity of the global physical dysfunction, exposed to the effects of chronic diseases and conditions associated with aging, and the increased perception of regular physical activity, to a lesser degree, can have a positive impact on health, daily functioning, and the quality of adult life presents a compelling argument for changing methods. Scientists, policymakers, and practitioners are drawn to this important public health arena.

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